

A REVIEW ON FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT TRENDS AND DEVELOPMENTS IN THE PHILIPPINES

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Abstract: *Financial management in the Philippines is rapidly changing as traditional practices meet new technologies and national development goals. The country's financial situation shows a mix of promoting inclusion using digital solutions and tackling ongoing challenges. This paper looks at the trends and changes in financial management in the Philippines focusing on key principles, financial literacy, institutional practices, new innovations, and ongoing issues. Financial inclusion recognized as a national priority, it has influenced many of the country's financial strategies. The study highlights financial literacy as essential for helping individuals and businesses make informed financial choices, use digital platforms effectively and protect their financial health. In institutional level businesses and financial organizations face growing pressure to keep up with technological changes while also managing risks and compliance. The integration of sustainability, especially through environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors reflects the broader scope of financial management both locally and globally. New trends such as digital payments, blockchain and artificial intelligence show how innovation is changing the landscape. However, these also raise concerns about cybersecurity, regulation, and unequal access to financial knowledge. The review concludes that the future of financial management in the Philippines relies on finding a balance between innovation and stability, improving financial literacy and ensuring flexible regulations. By focusing on these priorities, the Philippines can create a more inclusive, strong, and sustainable financial system that fosters both economic growth and social development.*

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Introduction

Financial management in the Philippines has changed a lot in recent decades. Economic, technological and regulatory factors have all played a role. The Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP) sees financial inclusion as an important part of national development. This shows the need to help more Filipinos access essential financial services (Desello & Agner, 2023). This national goal reflects the understanding that financial management is not just an economic need but also a way to promote social equity and national progress.

A major force behind these changes is the growth of digital technology. As digital interactions and mobile payments become more common both banks and non-bank providers are offering more services online and through social media (Celestino et al., 2024). This shift forces businesses and individuals to change their financial practices in areas like transaction processing, risk assessment, and customer relationship management (Černevičienė & Kabašinskas, 2024). The increased reliance on technology shows the need for financial systems to balance innovation with security and inclusivity.

Financial literacy is another essential aspect of financial management in the Philippines. It affects how individuals and institutions can make informed decisions. Research shows that there are still gaps in financial knowledge, especially among millennials and students. This is true even though they generally have a positive view of financial literacy (Dimaunahan et al.,

2025; Espiritu, 2022). Faculty members and professionals also face difficulties in demonstrating responsible financial behavior. This emphasizes the need for focused financial education programs (Carvajal et al., 2025). Studies indicate that financial literacy is critical not just for personal finance well-being but also for helping people effectively use digital financial services and protect their consumer rights (Zheng et al., 2024).

At the institutional level, larger financial institutions face complex challenges in managing credit, market, and operational risks while following regulations like capital adequacy and solvency requirements (Mani, 2024; Asadi & Janabi, 2020). These institutional factors show how closely financial literacy, risk management, and regulatory compliance are connected in maintaining economic stability.

New trends like FinTech, artificial intelligence and sustainable finance are changing the future of financial management. The growth of digital payments, peer-to-peer lending, and blockchain brings both opportunities and challenges for the financial system (Celestino et al., 2024; Mani, 2024). Additionally, concerns about sustainability are pushing institutions to include environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors in financial decisions (Vergara & Agudo, 2021). These trends indicate a changing landscape in which innovation, inclusion, and sustainability will shape the future of financial management in the Philippines (Sharma et al., 2024).

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Literature Review

Foundations of Financial Management in the Philippines

The foundational principles of financial management in the Philippines are largely shaped by its dynamic economic landscape and evolving regulatory environment. Financial inclusion is recognized by the Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP) as a national development agenda requiring concerted efforts across various sectors to accelerate its societal benefits (Desello & Agner, 2023). This indicates a strategic emphasis on expanding access to financial services for the broader population.

Technological advancements have significantly influenced the financial sector with digital interactions and payments becoming increasingly common (Celestino et al., 2024). Financial institutions including both non-bank providers and traditional banks have expanded into the digital space offering a wider financial products and services, often through social media platforms (Celestino et al., 2024). This digital shift alters the operational context for financial management demanding adaptation in areas such as transaction processing, risk assessment and customer relationship management (Černevičienė & Kabašinskas, 2024). For instance, the foreign exchange market a critical component of the financial system sees a significant proportion of its activities dedicated to credit management 60% and risk management 23% with automated and smart investment accounting for 15% (Černevičienė & Kabašinskas, 2024). This highlights the complex

interplay of traditional financial functions with emerging technologies.

The broader context of financial systems development is also influenced by global trends and the pursuit of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Financial technology is connected to economic factors and can enhance financial inclusion, improve the efficiency of financial markets and drive economic growth by facilitating better access to capital (Yu & Huarng, 2024). This underscores how the evolution of financial management is intertwined with national development objectives and technological integration.

Financial Literacy and Capabilities

Financial literacy is a critical determinant of effective financial management, particularly in the Philippine context. It plays a pivotal role in improving personal financial management and assisting individuals in achieving financial objectives (Dimaunahan et al., 2025). For millennials, who constitute a significant portion of the working-age demographic and key consumers financial literacy is especially important (Dimaunahan et al., 2025). Studies reveal existing gaps in financial literacy levels and suboptimal financial decision-making among Filipinos (Dimaunahan et al., 2025).

Research among college faculty members in the Philippines underscores the importance of financial literacy and debt management, as faculty members are crucial in modeling responsible financial behavior despite often facing financial challenges themselves (Carvajal et al., 2025). Similarly, among business

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administration students in urban colleges in the Philippines there is a general positive attitude towards financial literacy though knowledge levels vary significantly with demographic factors (Espiritu, 2022). These findings highlight the need for targeted financial education initiatives across different segments of the population.

Financial literacy also acts as a fundamental component of financial management capabilities. For instance, an assessment of personnel in a state university in the Philippines identified financial literacy as one of three key aspects of financial management emphasizing its role in achieving financial autonomy (Contreras et al., 2021). The ability to safeguard financial consumer rights particularly against fraud is also positively impacted by financial literacy alongside information attention, digital literacy, and social interaction (Zheng et al., 2024). This suggests that financial literacy empowers individuals to navigate complex financial environments and protect their interests.

Within the context of FinTech adoption financial literacy is an influencing factor (Firmansyah et al., 2022). Higher financial literacy allows individuals to better understand and utilize digital financial products and services which can contribute to a reduction in household multidimensional poverty by enabling more informed investment and borrowing decisions (Wang et al., 2024). This is particularly relevant in microfinance services where financial literacy mediates the impact of FinTech adoption (Hasan et al., 2024).

Financial Management Practices of Businesses and Institutions

Financial management practices among businesses and institutions in the Philippines are increasingly influenced by technological integration and the need for risk management. Financial literacy significantly influences SME performance consistently showing higher financial literacy promotes entrepreneurs' financial management capabilities and enhances business outcomes (Abdallah et al., 2024). The integration of FinTech coupled with financial literacy is shown to influence financial management behavior among accounting students with FinTech payments exerting a significant influence (Agnas et al., 2024).

For larger financial institutions the landscape is complex involving continuous adaptation to economic, technological, and regulatory shifts (Mani, 2024). This includes managing credit risk, market risk, and operational risk which are critical for stability (Mani, 2024). The financial sector also faces the imperative to comply with evolving regulations such as those governing capital requirements. The Solvency II agreement, for example, sets forth requirements for determining Solvency Capital Requirement (SCR) for insurance companies emphasizing the need for robust internal models for risk measurement (Asadi & Janabi, 2020).

The management of financial institutions involves not just internal controls but also external environments. Supervisory review processes and market discipline through transparency and disclosure exert pressure on

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institutions to manage risks effectively (Asadi & Janabi, 2020). This complex system ensures that financial institutions function within proper risk limits while supporting overall economic stability.

Emerging Trends in Financial Management

The field of financial management is experiencing rapid transformation driven by technological innovations particularly in FinTech. This includes the emergence of digital payments, crowdfunding, peer-to-peer lending, and blockchain technology all of which are reshaping traditional financial services (Celestino et al., 2024; Mani, 2024). Bibliometric analyses confirm a significant increase in FinTech-related publications highlighting its growing importance (Syamsiah, 2025; Abdo et al., 2025).

FinTech's role in promoting financial inclusion and sustainable development is a prominent trend (Vasishta & Singla, 2024; Kishor et al., 2024). FinTech's ability to enhance efficiency and reduce costs makes financial services more accessible to a broader customer base including the unbanked population (Vasishta & Singla, 2024; Kishor et al., 2024). In developing countries FinTech-driven inclusive finance has been shown to induce bank profitability (Zheng et al., 2023).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and machine learning are also emerging as key technologies in finance. AI-powered financial advisors or robo-advisors offer personalized financial advice at lower costs improving accessibility for those who cannot

afford traditional services (Kofman, 2024; Macaumbao and Bandera, 2025). Explainable AI (XAI) is becoming crucial for justifying decisions made by complex financial models enhancing trust and improving risk assessment (Černevičienė & Kabašinskas, 2024). The overall structure of financial technology research shows areas like RegTech and cybersecurity, robo-advisory and algorithmic trading, cryptocurrencies, digital payment systems, lending platforms, and crowdfunding as significant sub-areas (Mani, 2024).

Furthermore, sustainability is gaining traction with an increasing focus on integrating environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors into financial decisions (Vergara & Agudo, 2021). Sustainable finance aims to promote long-term economic development by considering ESG factors (Mani, 2024; Macaumbao & Bandera, 2025).

The future of financial management is characterized by a "digitalized financial revolution" encompassing blockchain technology and financial inclusion as well as an emphasis on "innovation, entrepreneurship & financial market" and "sustainable business development" (Sharma et al., 2024).

Challenges and Issues in Financial Management

Despite advancements financial management in the Philippines faces several challenges. Low levels of financial literacy and poor financial decision-making persist among segments of the population including millennials (Dimaunahan et al., 2025). While positive attitudes towards

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financial literacy exist, knowledge varies indicating persistent educational gaps (Espiritu, 2022).

The rapid evolution of FinTech introduces new complexities. While FinTech offers numerous benefits it also presents issues concerning consistency, cybersecurity, and regulatory frameworks (Celestino et al., 2024). For instance, the use of FinTech platforms for illicit money transfers such as money laundering is a growing concern necessitating careful consideration of financial regulations (Usman et al., 2024). Systemic financial risk can also be induced by financial leverage volatility a phenomenon observed in fast-growing FinTech sectors (Zheng et al., 2022).

The adoption of FinTech can be influenced by various factors including perceived risk which users assess based on potential financial losses, privacy breaches, and security vulnerabilities (Amnas et al., 2023). Trust in FinTech provider's reputation, service quality, and perceived regulatory support are critical in mitigating these risks (Amnas et al., 2023).

The broader financial environment also poses challenges. While digital financial inclusion can reduce household multidimensional poverty its effectiveness is contingent on factors such as credit availability, social capital, non-agricultural employment and particularly the strength of the financial environment including financial supply, household financial literacy and government financial supervision (Wang et al., 2024). This implies that technological solutions

alone are not sufficient; a supportive ecosystem is essential for optimal outcomes.

Implications and Future Directions

The trends and challenges identified in financial management in the Philippines have significant implications for various stakeholders and suggest clear future directions. The emphasis on financial inclusion as a national development agenda highlights the need for continued efforts to expand access to financial services, leveraging FinTech as a key enabler (Desello & Agner, 2023; Vasishta & Singla, 2024).

Improving financial literacy and capabilities across all demographics is crucial for empowering individuals and businesses to make informed decisions and harness the benefits of emerging financial technologies (Carvajal et al., 2025; Dimaunahan et al., 2025; Espiritu, 2022; Zheng et al., 2024). Educational programs and initiatives focused on practical financial skills, debt management, and understanding digital financial products are vital (Carvajal et al., 2025; Wang et al., 2024).

From a business perspective, the integration of FinTech into financial management practices is inevitable and requires strategic adoption, careful risk management, and adaptation to new operational models (Agnas et al., 2024; Ningsi et al., 2024). For MSMEs, FinTech offers opportunities for increased financial access and inclusiveness, which can drive innovation and growth (Rahayu et al., 2023; Nugraha et al., 2022). However, this must be accompanied by enhanced digital financial literacy and robust cybersecurity measures.

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The regulatory landscape must evolve to keep pace with technological innovations. This includes developing frameworks that promote financial innovation while mitigating risks like money laundering and systemic financial instability (Celestino et al., 2024; Usman et al., 2024; Zheng et al., 2022). The role of RegTech, which involves using technology for regulatory compliance will become increasingly important (Mani, 2024).

Future research should continue to explore the dynamic interplay between FinTech, financial inclusion, and sustainability (Kishor et al., 2024). Areas such as the ethical implications of AI in finance the impact of blockchain on financial infrastructure, and the development of green finance initiatives warrant further investigation (Černevičienė & Kabašinskas, 2024; Sharma et al., 2024; Vergara & Agudo, 2021; Song et al., 2024). Understanding the nuances of FinTech adoption drivers including cultural and behavioral factors specific to the Philippines will also be critical for successful implementation (Firmansyah et al., 2022; Amnas et al., 2023). Ultimately, the route of financial management in the Philippines will be shaped by a concerted effort to foster innovation, enhance financial literacy, strengthen regulatory oversight, and embed sustainability principles across the financial ecosystem.

Methodology

This study employed a systematic literature review (SLR) approach to examine the trends, developments, and challenges in financial management within the Philippine context. The

methodology was designed to ensure a comprehensive synthesis of existing knowledge and identify gaps for future research. A qualitative and descriptive research design was adopted focusing on analyzing existing academic and institutional literature on financial management practices, financial literacy, technological innovation, and sustainability.

This design allowed for an in-depth exploration of conceptual developments and empirical findings relevant to the Philippines. Peer-reviewed journal articles, policy papers, institutional reports and digital publications from 2020 to 2025 were selected. Databases and platforms such as Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, ResearchGate, and the Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP) website were used to retrieve relevant materials. The inclusion of both local and international sources ensured that global financial trends were linked to Philippine applications and implications. Studies were included that discussed financial management, financial literacy, FinTech, or sustainability within the Philippine context or in developing economies with similar financial structures and provided empirical or conceptual insights applicable to financial institutions, businesses, or individual consumers. Patterns, similarities, and differences across studies were analyzed to identify the current state and direction of financial management in the Philippines. The analysis also integrated international perspectives to contextualize global financial trends locally.

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Results and Discussion

The findings reveal that financial inclusion remains a central national objective, driven by the BSP's initiatives to expand digital access to financial services (Desello & Agner, 2023). Financial technology (FinTech) innovations such as mobile banking, e-wallets and online payment systems have significantly increased financial accessibility for unbanked populations (Celestino et al., 2024). This digital transformation has redefined how financial management operates, encouraging more efficient transaction systems and data-driven decision-making. However, the rapid digitalization also introduces new concerns such as cybersecurity, system reliability, and the risk of technological exclusion among low-income groups.

A recurring theme across studies is the critical role of financial literacy in effective financial management (Dimaunahan et al., 2025; Espiritu, 2022). The review highlights that despite growing awareness, significant gaps persist among Filipinos particularly among the youth and low-income earners. Financial literacy not only improves personal financial stability but also enhances the capacity of individuals and MSMEs to adopt digital financial tools and manage credit responsibly (Contreras et al., 2021; Rahayu et al., 2023). This underscores the need for sustained financial education programs embedded in both formal and informal learning systems.

The literature emphasizes the growing integration of artificial intelligence (AI),

blockchain, and machine learning into financial management systems (Macaumbao & Bandera, 2025; Kofman, 2024). These technologies enhance efficiency, predictive analytics, and real-time decision-making. Yet, the studies caution against overreliance on automation which could amplify risks related to algorithmic bias, data privacy, and ethical decision-making (Černevičienė & Kabašinskas, 2024). Robust risk management frameworks are needed to balance innovation with governance especially in sectors such as insurance and banking where capital adequacy and solvency requirements are stringent (Asadi & Janabi, 2020).

Recent studies show that the Philippine financial system is gradually incorporating Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles in decision-making (Vergara & Agudo, 2021; Mani, 2024). Financial institutions are encouraged to align investment portfolios with sustainable development goals (SDGs) promoting “green finance” initiatives. Sustainable financial management ensures long-term growth by mitigating environmental and social risks which are increasingly relevant in global financial reporting and investment strategies.

Despite significant progress, challenges persist most notably the uneven adoption of FinTech due to limited trust, regulatory inconsistencies, and cybersecurity vulnerabilities (Amnas et al., 2023; Usman et al., 2024). Additionally, systemic financial risks arise from financial leverage volatility within fast-growing FinTech sectors (Zheng et al., 2022). To address these

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issues, researchers advocate for regulatory innovation (RegTech), strengthened public-private cooperation and continuous upskilling of the financial workforce to keep pace with digital demands.

Conclusion

Financial management in the Philippines is undergoing significant change as traditional practices converge with modern innovations. The increasing use of digital technologies the expansion of financial services and the growing importance of sustainability are reshaping how individuals, businesses, and institutions manage their finances. These developments present opportunities for growth and inclusion but also introduce new risks and responsibilities that require careful attention. The core of this

transformation is the need for stronger financial literacy. Individuals must be equipped with the knowledge and skills to make sound financial decisions while institutions must adopt practices that balance innovation with stability. Effective risk management, regulatory adaptability and a commitment to sustainable practices are all essential for building a financial system that can respond to both local and global challenges.

Philippines must continue to strengthen education, improve access to financial services, and promote responsible innovation. By doing so, the country can create a financial environment that empowers people, supports business development, and contributes to long-term national progress.

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